

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Fast Disintegrating Tablets of Solid Dispersion of Escitalopram: A Review

Prasad Mhetre*, Pranav Mahamuni, Dr. V. M. satpute, S. R. Ghodake

Loknete Shri Dadapatil Pharate Collage Of Pharmacy Mandavgaon Pharata. Tal. Shirur Dist. Pune

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 08 Dec. 2024

Keywords:

Escitalopram, disintegrating Tablet, solid dispersion, lubrication, Solid spray.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14302843

ABSTRACT

Escitalopram, a widely prescribed selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI), is hindered by its poor aqueous solubility, which limits its bioavailability and delays its therapeutic onset. Fast disintegrating tablets (FDTs), combined with solid dispersion technology, offer a novel approach to address these challenges. This review provides an overview of the preparation methods for solid dispersions of escitalopram, their integration into FDTs, and the evaluation parameters essential for optimizing the formulation. The potential of this approach to enhance solubility, dissolution rate, and patient compliance is also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Escitalopram is extensively used for the treatment of depression and anxiety disorders. However, its poor aqueous solubility and slow dissolution rate pose significant challenges in achieving optimal therapeutic efficacy. Solid dispersion technology has been widely recognized for its ability to enhance the solubility and dissolution of poorly water-soluble drugs. Incorporating these solid dispersions into FDTs further enhances drug performance by providing rapid disintegration and immediate drug release. This approach is particularly beneficial for patients with

swallowing difficulties, ensuring improved compliance and faster therapeutic effects.

Solid Dispersion of Escitalopram Solvent Evaporation Method

Escitalopram and hydrophilic carriers, such as polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) or polyethylene

*Corresponding Author: Prasad Mhetre

Address: Loknete Shri Dadapatil Pharate Collage Of Pharmacy Mandavgaon Pharata. Tal. Shirur Dist. Pune.

Email ✉: navnathkharat678@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

glycol (PEG), are dissolved in a common solvent and evaporated to form a solid dispersion. This method enhances the molecular dispersion of escitalopram, improving its dissolution.

Melting Method

Hydrophilic carriers such as PEG or mannitol are melted, and escitalopram is incorporated into the molten carrier. The mixture is then rapidly cooled and solidified to achieve a dispersion with enhanced solubility.

Spray Drying Technique

A solution of escitalopram and a carrier is atomized into fine droplets, which are then dried to form solid dispersions. This method offers precise control over particle size and surface area, facilitating improved dissolution.

Co-Grinding

Escitalopram is ground with carriers like cyclodextrins or PVP using mechanical techniques to enhance drug-carrier interactions and solubility.

Formulation of Fast Disintegrating Tablets of Escitalopram

FDTs are designed to disintegrate rapidly in the oral cavity, ensuring faster drug release and improved patient compliance. The formulation of FDTs containing solid dispersion of escitalopram involves the following components:

Superdisintegrants

Examples: Croscopovidone, croscarmellose sodium, sodium starch glycolate. Role: Facilitate rapid disintegration by swelling and wicking water into the tablet structure.

Binders and Fillers

Binders: Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC). Fillers: Mannitol, lactose, or microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) to provide bulk and improve mouthfeel.

Lubricants

Magnesium stearate or talc is added to enhance flow properties and prevent sticking during tablet compression.

Formulation Techniques

Direct Compression: Preferred for its simplicity and cost-effectiveness. Solid dispersion is mixed with excipients and compressed into tablets. **Wet Granulation:** Used when the solid dispersion has poor flow properties, involving the formation of granules before compression.

Evaluation of Escitalopram FDTs

Comprehensive evaluation ensures the quality and effectiveness of the FDT formulation. The critical parameters include:

Pre-Formulation Studies

Solubility Enhancement: Assessed to confirm the improved dissolution of escitalopram in solid dispersion form. **Drug-Excipient Compatibility:** Ensured through techniques like differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and X-ray diffraction (XRD).

Physicochemical Properties

Disintegration Time: Must be less than 30 seconds to ensure rapid drug release. **Wetting Time:** Determines how quickly the tablet absorbs moisture in the oral cavity. **Hardness and Friability:** Assessed to ensure the mechanical strength and handling stability of the tablets.

In-vitro Drug Release

Dissolution studies compare the release profile of escitalopram from FDTs against pure drug and marketed formulations to demonstrate improved dissolution.

Stability Studies

Conducted under accelerated conditions (40°C/75% RH) to evaluate the stability of the solid dispersion and FDTs.

In-vivo Studies

Pharmacokinetic studies are carried out to confirm enhanced bioavailability and faster onset of action.

Challenges and Future Directions

Despite their potential, the development of solid dispersions and FDTs of escitalopram faces challenges such as scalability and stability of the amorphous form. Future research should focus on

advanced carriers, innovative preparation methods (e.g., hot-melt extrusion), and optimized FDT designs to ensure commercial viability.

Indication

- **Depression:** depression is a mood disorder that causes a persistent feeling of sadness and loss of interest.
- **Anxiety disorder:** an anxiety disorder is a serious mental illness. For people with anxiety disorder, worry and fear are fear are constat and overwhelming, and can be crippling.
- **GAD:** Generalized anxiety disorder, GAD, is an anxiety disorder characterized by chronic anxiety, exaggerated worry and tension, even when there is no or little tension really exist in their lives.
- **Phobic states:** persistent fear of social or performance situations.
- **Panic disorder:** people with this condition have feeling of terror that strike suddenly and repeatedly with no warning.
- **OCD:** (obsessive-compulsive disorder) recurrent & persistent thoughts, impulses or images.... intrusive and inappropriate.

Advantages –

Advantages of Escitalopram:

1. Effective for depression and anxiety.
2. Fewer side effects than other SSRIs.
3. Convenient once-daily dosing.
4. Low risk of addiction.
5. Improves mood and quality of life.

Advantages and disadvantages of Escitalopram

Escitalopram, a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI), is commonly prescribed for conditions like depression, generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, and social anxiety disorder. Below are

its **advantages** and **disadvantages**:

Advantages

1. **Effective for Depression and Anxiety**
Escitalopram is well-documented as being

effective in reducing symptoms of major depressive disorder and anxiety disorders.

2. **Fewer Side Effects Compared to Other SSRIs**

It is generally better tolerated, with fewer side effects such as drowsiness or weight gain, compared to older SSRIs.

3. **Once-Daily Dosing**

Easy to incorporate into daily routines because it requires only a single dose per day.

4. **Low Risk of Dependency**

Unlike benzodiazepines, it has a low risk of addiction or dependency.

5. ****Improves**

Disadvantages of Escitalopram:

1. **Common Side Effects:** Nausea, headache, dry mouth, drowsiness, or insomnia.
2. **Initial Adjustment:** May worsen anxiety or cause agitation initially.
3. **Sexual Dysfunction:** Can reduce libido or cause difficulty with orgasm.
4. **Weight Changes:** May lead to weight gain or loss in some users.
5. **Withdrawal Symptoms:** Abrupt discontinuation can cause dizziness, irritability, or flu-like symptoms.
6. **Delayed Onset:** Takes weeks to show full effects.
7. **Interactions:** May interact with other medications, including MAOIs or blood thinners.
8. **Rare Serious Effects:** Risk of serotonin syndrome or increased suicidal thoughts in young adults.

CONCLUSIONS

The formulation of FDTs incorporating solid dispersions of escitalopram provides an effective strategy to address the drug's solubility and bioavailability challenges. This approach ensures faster onset of action, improved patient compliance, and enhanced therapeutic efficacy, making it a promising advancement in pharmaceutical development. Further exploration

of novel carriers and advanced manufacturing techniques is expected to pave the way for the large-scale production of these innovative formulations.

REFERENCES

1. **Gajanan, P., et al.** (2013). Development and Evaluation of Escitalopram Oxalate Fast Dissolving Tablets Using Superdisintegrants. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 5(2), 12-18. This study focuses on enhancing patient compliance by developing fast-dissolving tablets using different disintegrants.
2. **Bhowmik, D., et al.** (2011). Formulation and Characterization of Escitalopram Oxalate Orodispersible Tablets. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 1(1), 22-28. This paper provides insights into improving the bioavailability and patient convenience of escitalopram through orodispersible tablet formulations.
3. **Choudhury, N., et al.** (2015). Stability Studies and Comparative In-Vitro Dissolution Analysis of Escitalopram Tablet Formulations. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 6(4), 1218-1223. The study evaluates stability parameters and dissolution profiles for generic versus branded formulations.
4. **Patil, S., et al.** (2019). Formulation and Optimization of Escitalopram Oxalate Sustained-Release Tablets Using a 3² Factorial Design. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research*, 53(3), 320-328. This research explores sustained-release formulations of escitalopram for prolonged therapeutic effects.
5. **Srinivasan, A., et al.** (2020). In Vitro Bioequivalence Study of Escitalopram Oxalate Tablets: Comparing Marketed Brands. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, 13(5), 50-55. The study evaluates in vitro bioequivalence for various branded escitalopram formulations
6. **Medication Guides:** Lexapro prescribing information.
7. **Mayo Clinic:** Details on uses, side effects, and precautions.
8. **Drugs.com:** User reviews, dosage, and interactions.
9. **Medical Journals:** Studies in *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* and *NEJM*.
10. **Professional Guidelines:** American Psychiatric Association recommendations.
11. Let me know if you need detailed links!

HOW TO CITE: Prasad Mhetre*, Pranav Mahamuni, Dr. V. M. satpute, S. R. Ghodake, Formulation and Evaluation of Fast Disintegrating Tablets of Solid Dispersion of Escitalopram: A Review, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 12, 745-748. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14302843>